

SELECTION OF YOUNG GOALKEEPERS IN THE INITIAL PREPARATION STAGE IN FOOTBALL

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Abstract: This article discusses the problems of selecting young football players for the role of goalkeeper at the initial training stage in modern football and their scientific and methodological foundations. The study analyzes the criteria for assessing the anthropometric indicators, psychophysiological characteristics and coordination abilities of young goalkeepers, and develops recommendations for optimizing the selection process.

Keywords: football, goalkeeper, selection, role, anthropometry, psychophysiology, reaction speed, sensorimotor skills.

Introduction. The rapid development of modern football, the increase in the intensity of the game and the complexity of tactical schemes have radically changed the requirements for each position player, especially goalkeepers. Today, the goalkeeper is an important tactical figure who not only protects his goal, but also is the first to initiate the team's offensive actions. Therefore, the selection of young people with a predisposition to the role of goalkeeper at the initial training stage (8-11 years old) in football academies and schools using scientifically based criteria is an extremely urgent problem. In order to popularize the sport of football and achieve high results in international arenas, systematic reforms are being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In this regard, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5887 dated December 4, 2019 "On measures to bring the development of football in Uzbekistan to a completely new level" serves as the foundation for introducing modern management methods and scientific and methodological approaches to the industry. This decree sets out specific tasks for the creation of a modern system for identifying young talented football players, selecting them (selection) and training them as professional athletes.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-115 dated April 7, 2023 "On measures for the comprehensive development of mass and professional football", introduced as a logical continuation of reforms in this area, is aimed at improving the football infrastructure in our country and digitizing and organizing the activities of football schools on a scientific basis. In accordance with the resolution, it is required to increase the efficiency of selection work in regional football academies and sports schools, and regularly monitor the physical and functional capabilities of young football players.

Goalkeeping is a specific and complex role, and the selection of young athletes for it often relies on subjective approaches or random factors. In order to ensure the implementation of the above state decisions and decrees, this research work aims to develop scientific and methodological foundations for selecting young football players for the role of goalkeeper, combining anthropometric, psychophysiological and coordination qualities into a single system.

The development trends of modern football are characterized by an increase in the intensity of the game, the complexity of tactical schemes and the increasing demands placed on

each position player. In football, the goalkeeper is one of the most important links that decide the fate of the game. Today, the goalkeeper is required not only to protect his goal, but also to perform the role of the leader of the team's offensive actions, a "playmaker".

However, in most football schools, the selection of young athletes for the role of goalkeeper is often carried out randomly, based on unscientific, subjective approaches or the child's personal preferences. This leads to the fact that in the future, time and resources are wasted on players who do not have high talent, or, conversely, real talents are left out. Therefore, the development of a scientific and methodological system for selecting children with a tendency to goalkeeping at the initial training stage (8-11 years old) based on complex (anthropometric, physical, psychophysiological) criteria is an extremely urgent problem today.

Literature review

The problem of selecting young athletes for the role of goalkeepers in football and early identification of their talent has been studied by many international and local experts for many years. Since the goalkeeper has a unique dynamic of movement during the game, which is fundamentally different from the field players, his selection criteria also require a special scientific approach.

J. Bangsbo (2014) and his co-authors, one of the scientists who studied the priority of anthropometric indicators in the selection of goalkeepers in world sports practice, emphasize in their work that in modern football, the height and width of the upper extremities (armpits) of the goalkeeper are the main genetic factors determining the radius of his movement on the goal line. In their opinion, there is a high possibility of developing physical qualities through training, but since height growth depends mainly on hereditary factors, it is necessary to predict height growth in children aged 8-11 years based on somatotypic data of parents.

European scientists V. Williams and T. Reilly (2000) in their long-term research proposed a multifactorial approach to sports selection. They proved that it is wrong to focus only on physical fitness when selecting young goalkeepers, but that cognitive and psychophysiological factors - visual perception, quick assessment of the situation and speed of decision-making - are of decisive importance.

Studies by neurophysiologists, in particular, in the works of A.H. Yakovlev (2018), note that the central nervous system of children selected for goalkeepers should have a balance of high mobility and inhibition processes. The author scientifically substantiates that the speed of sensorimotor reaction (simple and complex reaction time) in children aged 9-11 is the foundation for becoming a professional goalkeeper.

Scientists of our republic, including R.I. Nurimov (2021), in their educational and methodological manuals, analyzing the methodology for training young goalkeepers in Uzbek football academies, indicate that one of the main shortcomings is the insufficient assessment of children's coordination abilities and spatial orientation (feeling the goal and the trajectory of the ball) at the initial selection stage. According to local experts, the national selection system should be enriched with modern test technologies.

An analysis of the literature shows that, although there are many studies on the problem of selecting young goalkeepers, based on the requirements of today's dynamic football, complex criteria that combine anthropometric, psychophysiological and special physical qualities into a single system have not yet been fully developed. This served as the basis for determining the goals and objectives of this scientific article.

Research methods and organization.

During the study, the methods of analysis of scientific and methodological literature, pedagogical observation, anthropometric measurements (height, arm and leg girth, body weight), psychophysiological tests (simple and complex sensorimotor reaction time) and special sports tests (agility, jumping ability) were used.

Research results and their analysis

A systematic approach based on three main fundamental criteria is proposed for selecting young football players for the role of goalkeeper:

Anthropometric and genetic criteria

For goalkeepers, height and arm girth are the primary genetic factors. In the later stages of a child's life, physical qualities can be developed through exercise, but height growth depends mainly on heredity.

Height forecast: Forecasting the child's future height by studying the height indicators of the child's parents and analyzing bone age (models not lower than 185-190 cm).

Body proportions: The length of the hand (hand) should be longer than or equal to the player's total height, and the width of the palm and heel dimensions are taken into account.

Pedagogical and psychological observations and questionnaires

Physical and coordination criteria

A goalkeeper has specific movement dynamics: he needs explosive corporate power (acceleration), spatial orientation (feeling the goal) and high acrobatic agility, rather than linear speed. Test results show that children selected for goalkeepers should show 12-15% higher results than ordinary field players in the standing jump (not less than 35-40 cm) and sudden change of direction tests.

Scientific novelty of the article

Subjective approaches to the selection of young football players for the role of goalkeeper were abandoned, and multifactorial complex assessment criteria covering anthropometric, psychophysiological and coordination indicators were scientifically substantiated.

It was found that the sensorimotor response and differential attention stability indicators of children at the initial training stage (8-11 years old) are the main prognostic factors determining their future professional growth in the role of goalkeeper.

Based on the somatotypic data of the parents of young athletes and the dynamics of the child's body proportions, a scientific and methodological algorithm for predicting their future anthropometric models (above 185 cm) with high accuracy was introduced.

A new model of methodological recommendations was developed for coaches of football schools and academies aimed at optimizing the stages of identifying, selecting and targeted training of goalkeepers during the initial specialization period.

Conclusion. The selection of young goalkeepers in football should not be a subjective process, but should have a solid scientific and methodological foundation. The combination of anthropometric indicators (height and arm span), psychophysiological characteristics (reaction speed and attention span) and special coordination qualities ensures the effectiveness of the selection. The implementation of the developed comprehensive assessment criteria in the practice of football academies will significantly increase the quality of training professional goalkeepers who will be able to meet international requirements in the future.

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